

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Pieterse**FIRST NAME:** Zola**PROGRAM CODE:** DMCR**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did not use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing is undertaken to argue a hypothesis or a statement. Three main types of academic writing can be identified. The first type is that of Descriptive, which describes a subject, person, place, or event (ECU University 2013, 1). The second type of academic writing is Expository, which explains a theory or concept, and the third type of academic writing is Argumentative, where a person presents an argument through reasoning and the use of evidence. This paper will concentrate on the argumentative style.

Therefore, certain aspects of academic writing need to be addressed, and guidelines have to be followed. In academic writing, it is necessary to acquire some academic writing skills, which will enhance not only the quality of the writing of the paper but will also add to the credibility of the author.

2) THE PROCESS

What is the reason a paper is written? This is probably the most critical question to be asked before any paper is written. Is the reason to answer a question, discuss a topic, argue a theory, or to persuade? In essence, in academic writing, a statement or hypotheses have to be defended. Therefore it is essential not to only state the hypothesis clearly, but also to define the terms and keywords. An argument is presented through reasoning and the use of evidence (Ibid.).

ECU University (2013) states that an academic paper consists of an Introduction, a Focus Statement, Main Body, and a Conclusion (1). EUCLID (2015) states that the

structure consists of an Introduction, Body, and Conclusion (8). In the Introduction, the broad context is set, and it will also contain relevant background information, which will lead the reader to the Focus statement. It is recommended to open with a short orientation and answer the research question with a thesis statement in the Introduction (Ibid.).

The Focus Statement or Thesis Statement is responsible for clarifying the purpose of the writing and outlines the scope of the paper. In the Main Body, the main points, as well as the Focus statement, are elaborated. The research question is answered by developing a discussion and showing the author's knowledge and understanding of the material in the Main Body as well (Ibid.). The task of the Conclusion is to tie together all the ideas. In this way, the Conclusion provides a summary of the main ideas, which are linked back to the Focus statement.

The author needs to ensure that he/she understands the meaning of the key terms as well as how to use them in the hypotheses statement. In order to achieve this, an academic essay should include relevant examples, supporting evidence and information from academic texts or credible sources (ECU University 2013, 1). In the Conclusion, it is necessary to re-summarize the main points and include a final, broad statement (Ibid.).

When the process is started, it is recommended to understand the scope of the topic the author is writing about. The author has to ensure to comprehend not only the meaning of the argument but also the boundaries of the topic. A great idea is to draw up an initial plan or layout of ideas on the topic (EUCLID 2015, 1). This guideline or outline will ensure that the author stays on track and stay within the scope of the research.

After drawing up the initial plan, the research component of the paper starts. Credible sources (not Wikipedia) have to be researched. While researching academic sources, one source may lead to another, and it is useful to follow up resources that are used in one paper, to expand the literature search and to verify the sources that are used. It is recommended to contact the authors of papers as well and to discuss their research. It is also recommended to read broadly to get an overall picture of the topic. While reading, the author can commit to a tentative position and be open to research that disproves his/her standpoint.

When the initial research is completed, the actual writing of the paper can commence. When writing an academic paper, it is essential to follow specific guidelines regarding style and format (University of Technology Sydney 2000, 1). These will be discussed briefly.

"A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of your style that needs to be consistent" (EUCLID 2015, 52). The aforementioned implies that a particular style of writing, suitable to the specific audience, needs to be followed. Examples of different styles are that of technical, journalism, commercialism, or academic. Following a specific style ensures that the finished product represents the style of the publication and not that of the author.

Style encompasses the following aspects, such as sentence length, manuscript layout, font usage, and spelling (Ibid.). Academic writing thus implies that a particular style of writing, suitable to the specific audience, needs to be followed. There is also a significant difference between British English and American English format. Whichever language is used. The author needs to stay consistent throughout the writing process and keep to a specific style of language.

When sources are referenced, a particular style of reference needs to be followed. Examples of this can be the APA (American Psychological Association) or the Turabian style. Of utmost importance is to cite any paraphrases, references, or direct quotations. Academic research requires researchers to read and review the work of other writers, and it is obligatory to cite these authors or, the researcher will be plagiarizing the work of other authors. The type of referencing that is used needs to be consistent throughout the paper and be applied correctly according to the specific guidelines.

After writing the first draft of the paper, the Introduction and Conclusion are written. The author will find it necessary to redraft the writing a few times and” the author, will need to do more research in a particular area to strengthen an argument and provide evidence (University of Technology of Sydney 2000, 4).

It is a good idea to set aside the draft for a while to re-read it at a later time. After reading through it a second and third time, correct any mistakes and ensure that the Reference guide is correct. It also is a good idea if the author reads the paper out loud (EUCLID 2015, 38). When going over the final draft, the following aspects need to be addressed, namely that of structural, grammar, and punctuation, as well as technical aspects (University of Technology of Sydney 2000, 4). Ask someone, a friend or mentor, to read through the final draft and correct any mistakes.

When the process is done, the following questions have to be asked of the self to ensure that the paper the research questions and is within the framework of the hypothesis. These questions can be summarized as follows:

“Have I answered the question as directly and comprehensively as possible? Does the argument make sense? Is it balanced and well researched? Is the evidence relevant to and supportive of my argument? Have I used a consistent citation style? Have I referenced all my quotes and paraphrases? If there were any special instructions or guidelines for this assignment have I followed them?” (EUCLID 2015, 4).

3) CONCLUSION

Successful academic writing needs to be planned thoroughly before the actual writing starts. When doing research, it is essential to not only research academic papers that support the author's point of view but also be open to information that opposes their viewpoint as well. A specific style and format need to be followed in writing the paper. Most importantly, ensure that the style and format are applied consistently throughout the

paper. It is also crucial to remember to cite the work of other authors and give them the deserved credit. Finally, as an author, ensure to understand the concepts and keywords and to stay within the scope of the hypothesis and argument statement.

REFERENCES

| ECU University. 2013. *Academic writing*. <https://ecu.au.libguides.com/academic-writing/writing-process>. (Accessed November 18, 2019).

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EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack*. Washington, DC: Euclid University Press. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401d-period-1>. (Accessed August 1, 2019).

| University of Technology of Sydney. 2000. *Academic writing process*. https://www.uts.edu.au/sites/default/files/article/downloads/Academic_writing_process.pdf. (Accessed November 18, 2019).

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.